

Fermat's Last Theorem:

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

final proof

Therefore $(Z - X)$ must be n -th power.

$$Z - X = R^n$$

By same logic about $(Z - Y)$,

$$Z - Y \neq p$$

$$Z - Y \neq p^2$$

$$Z - Y = p_1^n \times p_2^n \times \cdots \times p_k^n$$

$$\therefore Z - Y = L^n$$

Therefore $(Z - Y)$ must also be a n -th power.

But $L = R = 1$ is impossible. Because it means that

$$X = Z - R^n = Z - 1$$

$$Y = Z - L^n = Z - 1$$

$$(Z - 1)^n + (Z - 1)^n = Z^n$$

$$2(Z - 1)^n = Z^n$$

$$2 = \frac{Z^n}{(Z - 1)^n}$$

2 is not a n -th power. So it is contradiction and it is impossible.

Therefore at least one of R and L is a natural number greater than or equal to 2.

$$\text{i) } (Z - X) = R^n \text{ (n-th power)}$$

$$\text{ii) } (Z - Y) = L^n \text{ (n-th power)}$$

Therefore the following two forms are that (X, Y, Z) must be satisfied at the same time.

$$\text{i) } (X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

$$\text{ii) } (X, Y, Z) = (LB, Z - L^n, Z)$$

$$\text{i) } (X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

$\gcd(R, A) = 1$. Because if not, $\gcd(R, A) = g \geq 2$,

Y^n is a multiple of g^{2n} .

$$(Z - R^n)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

If we expand, Z^n on both sides are canceled and

$$\left\{ -\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} R^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} (R^n)^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 (R^n)^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z (R^n)^{n-1} - R^n \right\} + Y^n = 0$$

all terms except $-\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} R^n$ are multiples of g^{2n} .

$\gcd(g, n) = 1$. If not, Y is a multiple of n , which is contradiction.

$\gcd(g, Z^{n-1}) = 1$. If not, Z and $Y = RA$ have a common divisor g .

ii)

The same logic applies to ii).

$$\gcd(L, B) = 1$$

$$\gcd(L, Z) = 1$$

$$\gcd(B, Z) = 1$$

i) $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$

$$(Z - R^n)^n + (RA)^n = Z^n$$

$$R^n A^n = Z^n - (Z - R^n)^n = (R^n) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

$$A^n = \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

Let's check the case $n = 3$.

$$A^3 = Z^2 + ZX + X^2 \quad (\alpha 1)$$

Add ZX to both sides.

$$A^3 + ZX = Z^2 + 2ZX + X^2 = (Z + X)^2$$

$$(Z + X) = \sqrt{A^3 + ZX}$$

(Since Z, X, A are all natural numbers, we choose positive value)

$$\therefore Z = \sqrt{A^3 + ZX} - X$$

$$Z = \sqrt{A^3 + ZX} - X \quad (\alpha 2)$$

Both the LHS and RHS have a variable Z .

Let's substitute $Z = \sqrt{A^3 + ZX} - X$ into the RHS variable Z .

Then,

$$Z = \sqrt{\left\{A^3 + \left(\sqrt{A^3 + ZX} - X\right)X\right\}} - X$$

Again, $(Z = \sqrt{A^3 + ZX} - X)$ is substituted.

$$Z = \sqrt{\left[A^3 + X \left\{ X \sqrt{\left(A^3 + X \left(\sqrt{A^3 + ZX} - X \right) \right) - X} \right\} \right]} - X$$

It is the form of $Z = \sqrt{\quad} - X > 0$ is substitute infinitely.

Let's see equation $(\alpha 2)$.

$\sqrt{A^3}$ is necessarily greater than some natural number K .

Note that $K \leq \sqrt{A^3}$ and think about

$$Z = \dots \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}}}}$$

Each of $\sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}}$ is bigger than $\sqrt{A^3}$.

$$\sqrt{A^3} < \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}}$$

Since Z is a natural number, each value of A^3 that escapes the root must be a natural number. If not, there is an irrational number in the root, Z can never be a natural number.

Lemma 14. Let

(*natural number*) = N , (*irrational number*) = I

(*rational number*) = Q

Then the following always holds:

$$\sqrt{N + I} = I$$

pf) Suppose not.

$$\sqrt{N + I} = Q$$

Square both sides.

$$N + I = Q^2 = Q$$

$$I = Q - N$$

It is contradiction.

This also holds true for any n th root.

$$\sqrt[n]{N + I} = Q$$

$$N + I = Q^n = Q$$

$$I = Q - N$$

Irrational number cannot express by
(*rational number*) – (*natural number*)

Therefore Lemma14 is true.

Then look at this.

$$\sqrt{A^3} < \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}}$$

Each $\sqrt{A^3}$ must be a natural number.

And $\sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}}$ also must be a natural number because if we let

$$\sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}} = W,$$

Next expression of Z is

$$Z = \sqrt{A^3 + W}$$

$$\sqrt{A^3} < \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}} < \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}}} \dots$$

Call it

Step1

Step2

Step k

All terms each must be a natural number. Therefore,

If we let $\sqrt{A^3}$ is a natural number that satisfies

$$K < \sqrt{A^3},$$

at least following is true:

$$K + 1 < \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}}$$

and also at least following is true:

$$K + 2 < \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}}}$$

⋮

$$K + \infty < \dots \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3} + \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}}}$$

As a result,

$$Z = \dots \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3 + \sqrt{A^3}}}$$

is infinite.

Same logic is possible for

$$Z = \sqrt{A^3 + ZX} - X$$

Step 1 is

$$\begin{aligned} Z(1) &= \sqrt{A^3 + X(\sqrt{A^3 + ZX} - X)} - X \\ &= \sqrt{A^3 - X^2 + \sqrt{A^3 + ZX}} - X \end{aligned}$$

By ($\alpha 1$),

$$A^3 - X^2 = Z^2 + ZX$$

$$Z(1) = \sqrt{Z^2 + ZX + X\sqrt{A^3 + ZX}} - X$$

$$\begin{aligned} Z(2) &= \sqrt{Z^2 + ZX + X\sqrt{A^3 + X(\sqrt{A^3 + ZX} - X)}} - X \\ &= \sqrt{Z^2 + ZX + X\sqrt{A^3 - X^2 + X\sqrt{A^3 + ZX}}} - X \\ &= \sqrt{Z^2 + ZX + X\sqrt{Z^2 + ZX + X\sqrt{A^3 + ZX}}} - X \end{aligned}$$

In the end for $Z(\infty)$,

$(Z^2 + ZX)$ appears infinitely many times.

Let $f(Z, X) = Z^2 + ZX$

$$Z = \sqrt{f(Z, X) + X\sqrt{f(Z, X) + X\sqrt{f(Z, X) + \dots}} - X}$$

$f(Z, X)$ is a natural number that satisfies $K < f(Z, X)$

and each step $(k+1)$ is bigger than step k and all steps are natural numbers.

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{f(Z, X)} &< \sqrt{f(Z, X) + X\sqrt{f(Z, X)}} \\ &< \dots \sqrt{f(Z, X) + X\sqrt{f(Z, X) + X\sqrt{f(Z, X)}}} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore in the end,

$$Z > \infty$$

Therefore there is no natural number solution (X, Y, Z) for

$$X^3 + Y^3 = Z^3$$

Now we can generalize it to the any prime exponent n .

If we substitute $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$ into the equation,
the equation is summarized as follows:

$$A^n = Z^{n-1} + Z^{n-2}X + \dots + ZX^{n-2} + X^{n-1} = \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

We can make RHS $(n - 1)$ -th power by add

$$a_k \sum_{k=1}^{n-2} Z^k X^{n-1-k} \quad (\text{let it } D)$$

for suitable natural numbers a_k .

Then,

$$A^n + D = (Z + X)^{n-1}$$

$$\sqrt[n-1]{A^n + D} = Z + X$$

$$\therefore Z = \sqrt[n-1]{A^n + D} - X$$

D contains the term $(n - 1)ZX^{n-2}$

Let

$$\{D - (n - 1)ZX^{n-2}\} = E$$

$$Z = \sqrt[n-1]{A^n + E + (n - 1)ZX^{n-2}} - X$$

Now if we substitute Z into Z infinitely,

$$\begin{aligned}
Z &= \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{A^n + E + (n-1)X^{n-2} \{ \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{A^n + E + (n-1)ZX^{n-2}} - X \}} - X} \\
&= \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{A^n + E - (n-1)X^{n-1} + \left((n-1)X^{n-2} \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{A^n + E + (n-1)ZX^{n-2}}} \right) - X}
\end{aligned}$$

Let

$$A^n + E - (n-1)X^{n-1} = g(Z, X)$$

Then $g(Z, X) > 0$ always holds. Why?

$E > 0$ is trivial.

$$A^n = Z^{n-1} + Z^{n-2}X + \dots + ZX^{n-2} + X^{n-1}$$

The number of terms in A^n is n .

And since $Z > X$, all terms

$$Z^k X^{(n-1)-k} \geq X^{n-1} \quad (0 \leq k \leq (n-1))$$

is holds. Therefore

$$A^n > (n-1)X^{n-1}$$

and

$$g(Z, X) > 0$$

for all exponent n .

$$\begin{aligned}
Z &= \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{A^n + E + (n-1)X^{n-2} \{ \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{A^n + E + (n-1)ZX^{n-2}} - X \}} - X} \\
&= \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{A^n + E - (n-1)X^{n-1} + \left((n-1)X^{n-2} \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{A^n + E + (n-1)ZX^{n-2}}} \right) - X}
\end{aligned}$$

Let

$$A^n + E - (n-1)X^{n-1} = g(Z, X)$$

$$Z = \dots \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{g(Z, X) + (n-1)X^{n-2} \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{g(Z, X) + (n-1)X^{n-2} \sqrt{(n-1) \sqrt{g(Z, X)}}}}}}$$

each steps must be natural number and

step $k < \text{step } (k+1)$ for $\forall k$.

$$\therefore Z = \infty$$

Therefore for all prime number n ,

there is no natural number solution (X, Y, Z) for

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

Thus Fermat's last theorem is true.

Thank you for reading.

Reference

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